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Kristiansand, Norway
2-4.06.2025

- Crowdfunding
- Cryptocurrency
- Digital Assets
- Digital Lending
- P2P Lending
- Buy Now Pay Later
- Prosocial Lending
- Microfinance
- Microinsurance
- Savings Groups
- Donation Raising
- Patronage
- Crowd-insurance
- Invoice Financing
- Mobile Money

Edited by:
Hasan Aydin Okuyan
Fengya Zhu

The current proceedings include a collection of extended abstracts of papers presented at the 4th International Conference on Alternative Finance Research, which was held in Kristiansand, Norway 2-4.06.2025.

Review Process

Papers submitted to this conference have been double-blind peer reviewed before final acceptance to the conference. Only full papers were accepted for consideration. Many thanks to the reviewers who helped ensure the quality of all the submissions.

The proceedings include extended abstracts only of papers by authors who wished to include their work in the proceedings on a voluntary basis.

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1. Parallel Paper Session 1B (09:30 -10:30)

“Economic Development”

Chair: *Dr. Hasan Aydin Okuyan*

1.1. Revisiting the Social Trust – Economic Growth Nexus: A Nonlinear

Approach

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Purpose

This study investigates whether the relationship between social trust and economic growth is nonlinear and seeks to determine the existence of an optimal trust level that maximizes economic growth. Prior literature mostly assumes a linear relationship, yet emerging studies suggest diminishing or threshold effects. This research aims to fill this gap by re-evaluating the trust-growth nexus using a nonlinear modeling strategy, thereby answering Bjørnskov's (2022) call for identifying potential trust thresholds.

Research Design and Methods

An unbalanced panel dataset comprising 99 countries from 1995 to 2022 was constructed using data from the World Values Survey (WVS), World Development Indicators (WDI), and World Governance Indicators (WGI). Key variables include social trust, GDP per capita, corruption control, unemployment, education expenditure, and trade balance. A nonlinear model was estimated using the Nonlinear Least Squares (NLS) method and Panel Threshold Regression Models (PTRM) to detect threshold effects of social trust on economic growth. Approximately 720 model specifications were tested to determine robustness. Three models (single, double, and triple thresholds) were used to explore nonlinearities in different trust intervals.

Findings and Results

The results confirm a nonlinear, threshold-based relationship between social trust and economic growth.

Trust has a statistically significant positive effect on growth only beyond specific threshold levels:

¹ H. Aydın OKUYAN has received financial support for this article from a scholarship granted by The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under the Scheme of the International Postdoctoral Research Fellowship Programme (2219).

- Single-threshold model: Trust impacts growth positively only above the median trust level (22.91%).
- Double-threshold model: Positive impact exists between 15–30%.
- Triple-threshold model: Strongest effects occur between 20–60%; no significant effect below 20% or above 60%. A positive relationship was identified in the range of 20–40%, while a negative relationship was observed in the range of 40–60%.

Statistical tests (R^2 , AIC, BIC, Durbin-Watson, VIF) confirm robustness and validity of the models. Variables like corruption and unemployment also significantly influence growth, while education expenditure and trade balance effects are statistically insignificant.

Originality and Contribution

This study is one of the first to apply PTRM to the social trust–growth relationship using a large, unbalanced panel dataset. It confirms that the trust-growth nexus is nonlinear and operates through critical threshold levels. The contribution is fourfold:

1. It provides empirical evidence for the diminishing returns of trust beyond a certain point.
2. It highlights that no significant effect of social trust on economic growth was found when trust levels were below 20% or above 60%.
3. Social trust was found to have a positive effect on economic growth when ranging between 20% and 40%, and a negative effect when ranging between 40% and 60%.
4. It responds to a research gap by integrating nonlinear econometric techniques into the social capital–economy debate.

Implications

Policy strategies should refrain from assuming a linear relationship between trust and economic growth. In countries with low levels of trust, increasing trust can significantly promote economic growth. However, in societies where trust exceeds 40%, further increases may prove inefficient due to diminishing returns or the presence of substitutive institutional mechanisms. Therefore, policies aimed at enhancing trust should

be targeted and take into account a country's existing level of trust. Moreover, the findings indicate that strengthening anti-corruption efforts and reducing unemployment are critical complementary strategies for fostering economic growth.

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2. Parallel Paper Session 1C (09:30 -10:30)

“Crowdfunding Regulation I”

Chair: *Dr. Thomas Neumann*

2.1. Digital lending and the Consumer Credit Directive 2023

Tanja Jørgensen, Aarhus University, Denmark

Purpose

The article investigates how the newly adopted Consumer Credit Directive 2023 (CCD II) responds to the challenges posed by digitalization in the consumer credit market, particularly in the context of preventing over-indebtedness. It analyses whether the directive's provisions adequately address emerging digital lending practices and the complexities introduced by novel financial actors such as digital platforms and crowdfunding services.

Research Design and Methods

The study adopts a doctrinal legal research method, examining the text of CCD II and comparing it to previous directives (CCD 1987 and CCD 2008). It systematically evaluates the directive's scope, definitions, and key regulatory mechanisms, particularly those relevant to digital credit services and actors like credit intermediaries and platforms. The analysis is contextualized within the framework of the EU internal market and consumer protection law, particularly Articles 114 and 169 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). This also results in considerations of legal policy.

Findings and Results

CCD II marks a pivotal shift from a focus on traditional consumer protection to a more proactive stance on preventing and remedying over-indebtedness (Arroyo Amayuelas, 2024). It expands the regulatory scope by (Jørgensen, 2024):

- Including new digital credit products (e.g., buy-now-pay-later loans, SMS loans).
- Regulating credit intermediaries and some platforms more stringently.
- Introducing principles of responsible lending alongside responsible borrowing.
- Enhancing pre-contractual information duties adapted for digital use.
- Requiring creditworthiness assessments with stricter criteria and procedural safeguards.

However, the directive's broad application and multiple exemptions create legal complexity. Particularly, consumer-to-consumer lending via platforms and crowdfunding services not acting as creditors or intermediaries remain under-regulated, creating potential regulatory gaps and fragmentation, especially in relation to the ECSPR (Alibrandi & Grossule, 2022). Also, the effectiveness of the directive will depend considerably on its implementation and enforcement in the EU Member States (Cherednychenko, 2024).

Originality and Contribution

The article provides a comprehensive legal analysis of CCD II in light of digital market developments and identifies the directive as a foundational reform. It contributes to academic discourse by offering a nuanced understanding of how EU consumer credit law has evolved in response to technological change and highlighting the tension between harmonization, market integration, and social protection goals.

Implications

The findings suggest that CCD II is a step toward a more adaptive and responsible consumer credit regime in the EU. However, its effectiveness will depend on consistent national implementation and future legal refinements, especially in addressing gaps in digital and peer-to-peer lending. The directive lays a foundation for better consumer protection, but further reforms may be necessary to ensure comprehensive coverage of all digital credit actors and practices in the future.

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2.2. Investor Classification under ECSPR

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Abstract

With ECSPR a new distinction between different categories of investors has been introduced. The distinction between sophisticated and non-sophisticated investors in ECSPR is inspired by the similar investor distinction in MiFID II. However, there are substantial differences between the investor classification known from MiFID II and the one introduced in ECSPR.

The paper examines the investor classification under ECSPR with a focus on clarifying how the classification is applied. The investor classification lays the foundation for investor protection under ECSPR as it directly impacts which investor protection rules apply to the investor in question. It is important for both crowdfunding service providers and investors to know what the investor classification is and how it is applied to be able to identify the obligations and rights they have according to the investor protection rules. Furthermore, with ECSPR introducing its own classification of investors it is essential to be aware of the content of the classification – and especially how it differs from the similar and familiar classification under MiFID II. Through analyses of the regulation and the European Council working documents the content and application of the ECSPR investor classification is clarified and discussed in the paper.

First, the paper analyzes the distinction between sophisticated and non-sophisticated investors and the classification criteria. The distinction is central to the investor protection rules under ECSPR as a non-sophisticated investor is better protected and has access to special rights. Besides clarifying the criteria to qualify as a sophisticated investor, it is also found that it is the investors themselves that are responsible for the classification and that the criteria are met. Under ECSPR, the crowdfunding service provider has four tasks related to the formalities of the submission and approval of a request for treatment as sophisticated investor. However, the crowdfunding service provider is not responsible for the assessment of whether the requesting investor meets the classification criteria.

Second, the paper addresses similarities and differences between the classification found in ECSPR and MiFID II, respectively. Even though the ECSPR investor classification is inspired by MiFID II, the two sets of categorizations of investors/clients are not the same. When comparing the two sets of classifications it is seen that the terminology used as well as substantial matters are different. In general, the classification criteria in ECSPR are more lenient than the ones found in MiFID II.

Third, the paper discusses whether the established differences between ECSPR and MiFID II are desirable. From the European Council working documents it is seen that the Council to some extent was aware of the risks of deviating from the MiFID II criteria. The Council argued that it was necessary for ECSPR to have its own investor classification to reflect the characteristics of investment-based crowdfunding. However, this decision can be criticized on several points. Even the few initiatives that can be highlighted as advantages, can also be seen as disadvantages – beauty is in the eye of the beholder.

Key Words: ECSPR, sophisticated investors, investor classification, MiFID II

3. Parallel Paper Session 2A (10:50 -11:50)

“Equity Crowdfunding I”

Chair: *Dr. Daniel Berliner*

3.1. Follow your heart? Value congruence and investors' decisions

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Kristjan Jespersen, Copenhagen Business School, Denmark

Purpose:

This study investigates the heterogeneity of non-professional (retail) investors' preferences in impact investing, specifically how value congruence between an individual's personal values and an investment's economic, social, and environmental performance shapes investment decision-making. The research is motivated by the expanding yet complex landscape of impact investing, which combines financial return with social and/or environmental objectives. The study tests whether personal value alignment can explain why retail investors favor certain impact investments over others. It also explores the additional influence of investment domain and collective investor behavior.

Research Design and Methods:

The research utilized a discrete choice experiment (DCE) within a simulated equity-based crowdfunding context. A sample of 547 active non-professional U.S. investors was recruited. Participants were repeatedly asked to allocate a hypothetical \$1,000 across various pairings of investment projects that systematically varied on key attributes: social performance, environmental performance, investment risk, funding level, revenue growth, and investment goal. Each participant faced nine choice sets within the food, energy, and generic (non-domain-specified) investment domains. Personal values were measured using validated scales for egoistic, altruistic, and biospheric orientations. Data analysis was performed using mixed logit models to estimate the influence of both project attributes and investor-specific characteristics on choice probabilities.

Findings and Results:

The results demonstrate that while economic performance and risk are the most influential factors in determining investment choices, environmental and social performance also exert significant positive effects. Investors' weight on these attributes significantly varies markedly among individuals, a heterogeneity robustly explained by personal values. Investors with stronger altruistic, biospheric, or egoistic orientations show a greater preference for social, environmental, or financial performance, respectively. The analysis further reveals that the actions of others influence investors—higher funding levels increase individual investment likelihood, indicating herding or social validation effects. The investment domain significantly moderates attribute relevance, with environmental performance being the most important in energy-related investments and social performance in food-related investments.

Originality and Contribution:

This study advances the literature by providing empirical evidence that personal values are a key driver of heterogeneity in investor preferences for impact (versus financial) attributes. It also demonstrates that the relevance of different performance metrics is domain-sensitive, highlighting the importance of materiality and context in impact investing. Finally, it illustrates the predictive power of value-based segmentation, which is actionable for crowdfunding platforms and entrepreneurs in targeting likely investors.

Implications:

Segmenting potential investors by personal values could enhance targeting efficiency and campaign design, leading to greater investment in social and environmental projects. Platform operators can tailor marketing and recommendation systems based on value congruence to increase conversion rates. The observed influence of peer behavior suggests that visible early support or endorsements may catalyze broader participation. The domain-dependent nature of attribute relevance also indicates the need for nuanced communication strategies, emphasizing relevant impact metrics based on sector (e.g., environment for energy, social for food).

3.2. The Value Relevance of Financial and Non-financial Information for Equity Crowdfunding Share Pricing

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Purpose

Our research aims to enhance the literature on the value relevance of financial and non-financial information from prior accounting studies in traditional financial markets, focusing on the ECF market. We investigate how ECF firms value their shares prior to each funding round by identifying the key financial and non-financial factors influencing pre-money valuations. Additionally, we examine how these factors change as firms mature.

Research Design and Methods

Our study utilizes an augmented dataset of 1,535 UK ECF firms that raised funds on Crowdcube and Republic European (formerly Seedrs) between 2011 and 2023, regardless of their success. To examine the value-relevance of financial and non-financial information in the share pricing process, we employ the log-linear model, a standard method used in the venture capital literature (Hand, 2005; Sievers et al., 2013). All regression models are estimated using the fixed-effect estimator that accounts for both round and sectoral dimensions.

Findings and Results

Our results show that both financial and non-financial information play a critical role in explaining the share prices offered to potential investors. Financial information is as significant as non-financial information for changes in pre-money valuations. Specifically, increases in cash, non-cash assets, long-term debts, and profitability are associated with higher pre-money valuations. With regard to non-financial information, factors such as the size of the entrepreneurial team, the team's experience, and their

educational background are positive predictors of pre-money valuations. Additionally, firms that have applied for patents and those with the support of professional investors prior to ECF campaigns tend to be valued higher than those without such advantages. This suggests that intellectual capital and social capital positively influence share prices. Moreover, the importance of financial and non-financial information does not show statistically significant differences across funding rounds, which contradicts findings in the venture capital market. Notably, firms are more likely to offer discounts to compensate for the absence of financial statements, resulting in lower valuations.

Originality and Contribution

This study makes several key contributions to the existing literature. It extends the accounting literature by examining the value relevance of financial and non-financial information in early-stage firm valuation, focusing on the ECF market, where investors may lack resources for thorough due diligence. Another contribution is that it offers entrepreneurial literature a new perspective on firm valuation, as ECF share prices are set solely by entrepreneurs, rather than negotiated with investors. Finally, we extend the ECF literature by examining determinants of share prices in the fixed price, first-come, and first-served mechanism commonly used on European platforms, contrasting with the auction allocation mechanism examined by Hornuf and Neuenkirch (2017).

Implications

Our findings provide paramount implications for researchers, entrepreneurs, investors, ECF platforms, and governments. We introduce financial and non-financial information drivers that ECF firms are based on to determine the share price offers to prospective investors. Besides, we show how these drivers change over each funding round and highlight potential factors that probably emerge in later rounds. These factors provide a foundational framework for evaluating and comparing share prices among firms and potential directions for future research to enhance this framework.

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3.3. Unequal funding expectations? Gender bias in crowdfunding decisions

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Purpose

In Sweden, research shows that lenders – despite the absence of supporting empirical data – perceive projects by female entrepreneurs as riskier investments than projects pitched by men (Malmström et al., 2018). By incorporating a more diverse pool of lenders, crowdfunding is believed to lead to more democratised access to funding compared to traditional financial channels. However, empirical evidence remains scarce and inconclusive. In this study, we investigate the potential presence of gender bias in lending crowdfunding in the empirical context of a project testing and commercialising a novel, sustainable technology – activities often associated with male project owners.

Research Design and Methods

To examine gender bias in lending crowdfunding, we employ a split-sample choice experiment based on a stratified sample of Swedish households. Respondents were presented with a hypothetical project involving the establishment of a testing facility for more sustainable car batteries made from forestry by-products, and were given the opportunity to lend money to the project in exchange for interest. Half of the participants were told the project was led by a female entrepreneur, while the other half were told it was led by a male entrepreneur; all other project attributes were identical. A total of 2 040 individuals participated in the experiment, and the data were analysed using a mixed logit model.

Findings and Results

Our findings suggest that gender bias is present in lending crowdfunding. Overall, the project led by a woman was more likely to secure funding than the one led by a man, regardless of the respondent's gender.

We also found that respondents interpreted project information differently depending on the gender of the project owner. Specifically, respondents were, on average, more sensitive to risk signals and interest rates when the project owner was female. Moreover, we observed gender-based differences among respondents: male participants were more sensitive to risk and interest rates when the project was led by a woman, whereas female respondents were more sensitive to the repayment amount when the project was led by a man.

Originality and Contribution

This study contributes to the literature on gender effects in lending crowdfunding by employing a split-sample choice experiment in which gender is the only varying factor. Additionally, by focusing on funding for novel technology development – an area where the presence of female entrepreneurs is scarce (Gafni et al., 2021) – we provide insight not only into gender bias in lending crowdfunding but also into the success of female entrepreneurs in a male-dominated field. Moreover, the study addresses the importance of signalling, recognising that potential backers may not simply prefer male over female project owners (or vice versa) but may instead interpret certain information differently depending on the gender of the project owner. We focus on two signals: (a) the willingness of the project owner to invest their own private capital; and (b) whether the project owner has established cooperation with the end users of the technology.

Implications

One important implication is that crowdfunding may promote more democratised access to funding novel projects, for example, through involving a lower share of ‘gatekeepers’ who may be biased against women. Crowdfunding could also help increase gender diversity on the supply side by enabling individuals with limited capital – a group in which women are often over-represented – to invest.

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4. Parallel Paper Session 2B (10:50 -11:50)

“Crowdfunding and Sustainability”

Chair: *Dr. Friedemann Polzin*

4.1. AI in Quantifying Sustainability Impact on Crowdfunding Outcomes:

Evidence from SDG-Aligned Campaigns

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Stefana Belbe, Babecs-Bolyai University

Lucia Gomez Teijeiro, Bern University of Applied Sciences

Codruta Mare, Babecs-Bolyai University

Karsten Wenzlaff, University of Hamburg

Introduction

This study explores the impact of sustainability goals on crowdfunding success, particularly through the use of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The research aims to demonstrate the role of alternative data in sustainable finance, focusing on predictive factors of campaign success, including sustainability alignment. The study uses AI techniques, including Large Language Models (LLMs), transformers, and RF classifiers, to analyze 15 years of Kickstarter campaign data. The findings highlight the need for more investigation into how crowdfunding can advance Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through "sustainability-oriented crowdfunding," supporting sustainable finance. The study also highlights the limited use of ML and AI techniques in studies, particularly on crowdfunding success versus sustainability and crowdfunding topics in general. The research aims to address this methodological deficiency by integrating AI with practical research to deepen the understanding of "sustainability-oriented crowdfunding."

Method

Our study used Large Language Models (LLMs) to assess the success of sustainability-aligned crowdfunding projects. The methodological pipeline involved retrieving textual data, calculating the alignment of campaigns to each SDG description, optimizing and validating the SDG classification solution, and investigating the impact of SDG-aligned campaigns. The analysis was performed in Python

using sentence transformers, scikit-learn for statistical and ML-based techniques, and nltk for NLP manipulations. The study also tested the validity of the SDG alignment labelling framework using human-annotated data from the Startnext crowdfunding platform. The impact of SDG alignment on campaign success was assessed using a Random Forest classifier, which offered transparency and explainability. The model's global performance was evaluated by the area under the ROC curve (AUC-ROC) and the importance of impurity-based characteristics.

The study analyzed the success rates of Kickstarter projects in relation to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The majority of campaigns were non-aligned, with the majority being successful. Aligned projects, however, were rare, with 36,268 successful campaigns and 23,188 failed. The most frequently represented SDGs were Sustainable Cities and Communities, Life on Land, and Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure. The success rates of SDG-aligned projects increased significantly since 2014, peaking in 2024 with 6,193 projects. The most common categories were educational books for children, eco-friendly gadgets, and sustainable clothing. The analysis confirmed that alignment with the SDGs is a significant predictor of crowdfunding success. The study also found that the geographical location of a crowdfunding campaign influences the success rates, with 78% of successful projects coming from developed regions.

Results

Our study analyzing successful crowdfunding projects found that 75% of them achieved a similarity score of at least 0.197, indicating a substantial alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The Random Forest classification model showed robust performance in distinguishing successful from unsuccessful projects. The SDG alignment similarity score was the most important feature, contributing 34% to the predictive power of sustainability alignment in crowdfunding success. The study highlights the strategic importance of SDG alignment, geographical context, and project quality in determining the success of crowdfunding campaigns. The research also found a correlation between SDG alignment and success, confirming the independent contribution of SDG alignment.

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5. Parallel Paper Session 2C (10:50 -11:50)

“Crowdfunding Regulation II”

Chair: *Dr. Cecilie Højvang Paulsen*

5.1. Navigating Convergence and Complexity: An Evaluation of the EU's

Functional Approach to Crowdfunding Regulation

Weiwei Deng, University of Groningen

Crowdfunding has become an integral part of the European financial system, offering new funding opportunities for SMEs and startups while also introducing unique regulatory challenges. To address these risks, the EU adopted a functional regulatory approach (Peters and Powers, 1985; Merton, 1995; Ferrarini 2017), integrating crowdfunding into the existing securities regulation through the European Crowdfunding Service Providers Regulation (ECSPR) — a lighter version of the MiFID II regime (Eugenia Macchiavello, 2018). This approach ensures coherence within the regulatory framework but remains rooted in a micro-transactional perspective, overlooking structural changes and systemic risks arising from the re-bundling of financial services by crowdfunding platforms. In this regard, the ECSPR has been praised as “smart regulation” (Zetsche et al, 2017) for its proportionate regulatory response. However, the ECSPR, grounded in the functional approach, fails to address the re-bundling risks introduced by crowdfunding and their broader impact on financial stability. This article critically evaluates the merits and limitations of the EU's functional approach to regulating crowdfunding, arguing that while pragmatic, it fails to provide a real norm for regulating crowdfunding, as it remains constrained by the existing EU institutional setting.

Keywords: Functional regulation, ECSPR, securities regulation, regulatory perimeter, re-bundling

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5.2. Reconsidering the Regulation of Non-Investment Crowdfunding Models

Dr. Thomas Neumann, Aalborg University

Purpose and method

The aim of the paper is to further the development of regulation applicable to non-investment crowdfunding models. The paper relies on Denmark as a case study to show how dual legal standards may apply. The goal of the paper is to explain why such an undesirable legal regime appears and how to better regulate non-investment crowdfunding models in the future. The legal dogmatic method is applied. While it resembles desk research in its technique, the legal dogmatic method allows both for finding the law (*de lege lata*) and may work as a basis for criticism and direction for the future (*de lege ferenda*).

Findings and results

The paper demonstrates that entrepreneurs are subject to dual legal standards and explains the legal reasons that lead to an undesirable regulatory practice for both public supervisory authorities as well as fundraising entrepreneurs. Furthermore, the paper identifies and discusses possible regulatory options not previously considered by the legislator or relevant ministry.

Originality and contribution

The paper is the first to identify the underlying principle-based complications that explain why dual legal standards may apply to non-investment crowdfunding models and why the current practice of the supervisory authority is futile. Hence, a need for revision of the law is supported by the legal analysis.

Three possible options for future regulation are identified, discussed, and criticised: legislative amendment as proposed by the legislator, strengthening the notion of *animus donandi* at the textual level, or deregulating public fundraising altogether. To the best of my knowledge, no scholar in the Nordic region has previously explained the legal, principle-based complexity underlying the dual-standard situation for crowdfunding models and the futility of public authority practice. Neither has any legal scholar, nor the

responsible legislator or crowdfunding lobbyists, considered regulatory alternatives which could strengthen both civil society's access to funding more broadly and reduce the costs of supervision and compliance.

Implications

The implications of the analysis in the paper are two-fold. First, that the quality of legislative changes is raised beyond that of the current legislative proposal, especially when it comes to clarity of the law, predictability for the citizen, and coherence with other regulation. Second, the paper contributes to the legal debate in the European Union regarding the possible unification of non-investment crowdfunding regulation in the EU. This agenda has been pushed into the background by the focus of the EU on the harmonization of investment-based crowdfunding models.

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5.3. Crowdfunding in Tunisia - Observations on the impact of regulation on platform behaviour

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Fatma Hakim, Tunis Business School-University of Tunis

Ana Odorović, University of Hamburg, University of Cambridge

Motivation

This paper discusses the unique Tunisian crowdfunding regulation, the Tunisian Crowdfunding Law (TCL), and its impact on the development of an ecosystem. The TCL is the only jurisdiction where donation-based and reward-based crowdfunding platforms must apply for a license, allowing crowdfunding for entrepreneurial activity. Tunisia is one of the few countries with capital controls on foreign platform activities. The authors have monitored the Tunisian crowdfunding market and worked closely with emerging platforms, gaining insights into their business models within the legal framework. The paper also discusses whether the TCL supports alternative financing mechanisms, particularly for small and medium enterprises. The article contributes to the field of crowdfunding research by closing a literature gap.

The Tunisian crowdfunding law (TCL) is compared to other regulations in the US, European, and Moroccan contexts. The TCL is more like the European regime, as it imposes regulatory compliance on platforms and issuers of securities and loans. The authors propose several research questions, including the size of the Tunisian crowdfunding market before the TCL, the existence of crowdfunding platforms before the law, the provisions of the TCL, the provisions of the crowdfunding implementation laws, and which platforms emerged after the law. The study also highlights the evolution of the crowdfunding ecosystem from 2014 to 2025.

The Tunisian Crowdfunding Ecosystem before the introduction of the regulation

The MENA region experienced a boom in crowdfunding activity between 2013 and 2018, with the largest volume of transactions in the Middle East subregion. However, between 2018 and 2020, the CF market experienced a decline due to non-participation of some platforms. North African transactions grew from 2019 to 2020, with Tunisia's market share increasing from 0.1 percent in 2019 to 4% in 2020. Tunisia's entrepreneurial ecosystem has evolved significantly, with the government launching the Startup Act in 2018 and international organizations supporting entrepreneurship.

Between 2014 and 2025, the crowdfunding law in Tunisia was developed and implemented by various actors, including public institutions, the Assembly of the Representatives of the People, the Council of Ministers, the Ministry of Industry and SMEs, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Digital Economy, the Ministry of Development, Investment, and International Cooperation, the Microfinance Supervisory Authority, the Central Bank of Tunisia, the Financial Market Council, the Agency for the Promotion of Industry and Innovation (APII), civil society organizations, and crowdfunding actors. The law was submitted to the parliament and faced new actors due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The OPP, a regulatory framework, was established by APII and supported by the ACM. The non-profit sector, represented by the Hanns-Seidel Foundation, has advocated for the integration of civic crowdfunding within the regulatory framework.

Since 2016, Tunisia has been developing crowdfunding platforms as an alternative financing source. Platforms like Fly'Yes and Cha9a9a have been established, raising funds for various causes. The emergence of crowdfunding as a global phenomenon and the emergence of crowdfunding laws in neighboring countries prompted legislative institutions to discuss legislative steps towards a crowdfunding law. In 2020, a multidisciplinary steering committee (COPIL) was established to oversee crowdfunding legislation, which was amended in 2019. The COVID-19 pandemic led to the adoption of a crowdfunding law in 2020, which introduced targeted tax incentives for crowdfunding. By 2025, platforms like Kickoff.tn and Ba9chcih.tn expanded, and the new tax code of the Finance Law introduced targeted tax incentives for

crowdfunding. Tunisia's commitment to fostering an entrepreneurial ecosystem using crowdfunding as a viable financing mechanism aligns with the entrepreneurial ecosystem theory, which emphasizes six key pillars for its sustainable development.

Conclusion

The Tunisian crowdfunding ecosystem is still in its infancy, but on a path to growth. The paper analyzes the ecosystem before and after the introduction of the regulation, revealing that no equity-based or lending-based crowdfunding platform has yet been licensed. The Tunisian crowdfunding law is unique in that it has its own licensing regime for donation-based and reward-based crowdfunding, excludes individual issuers raising funds for personal use or charitable causes, uses fixed investment limits instead of flexible ones, does not set criteria for disqualification of investors, and does not set a limit for the amount raised by an issuer per year.

The effects of the crowdfunding law on financial return crowdfunding are yet to be established due to the lack of follow-up decrees. Alternative finance, such as crowdfunding, appears to take longer to establish in Tunisia compared to the crowdfunding law in Morocco.

The progression of crowdfunding in Tunisia underscores its vital role in empowering the non-profit sector, particularly donation-based crowdfunding. To amplify this positive trajectory, it is imperative to revisit and amend current crowdfunding regulations to explicitly accommodate and support non-profit organizations. To cultivate a more inclusive and supportive environment for the non-profit sector, it is crucial to finalize and implement the necessary regulations under Law No. 36 and ensure that new legislative measures do not impose undue restrictions on NGOs, preserving their ability to secure diverse funding sources, including through crowdfunding.

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6. Parallel Paper Session 3A (15:10 -15:50)

“Mobile Money”

Chair: *Dr. Prince Baah-Peprah*

6.1. Factors driving entrepreneurship in Mobile Money agent business in Sub-Saharan Africa: Evidence from the Democratic Republic of Congo

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Abstract

Mobile money has proven its prowess in increasing financial inclusion in Africa, the continent with the lowest financial inclusion rate in the world. Agents have played a key role in providing access to mobile money services, bringing cash pick-up, cash deposit, and cash transfer services closer to the population in both cities and remote areas. While mobile money has shown high uptake in a few African countries, other nations still exhibit reduced use of the service compared to the potential offered by their large populations. The present study aims to investigate the factors driving Mobile Money Agent (MMA) business entrepreneurship in Sub-saharan Africa, with a specific focus on the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). A Discrete choice experiment and Mixed Logit Models are employed to derive the study's results. Results from the Mixed Logit Model show that the conditions offered by mobile money providers to agents, especially commission rates, days for registration of the business are the most important factors that influence aspiring entrepreneurs to venture into the MMA business, additionally, younger individuals are most likely to venture into MMA business and practical support from friends is needed to increase the intention to start a MMA business.

Key words:

Mobile money Agents, Entrepreneurship, DR Congo, Discrete choice experiment, Mixed logit model

7. Parallel Paper Session 3B (15:10 -15:50)

“Fraud”

Chair: *Karsten Wenzlaff*

7.1. The role of Fintech in Curbing Corruption and Financial Fraud: A New Indicator Based on Self-Reported Experiences

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Karoll Gómez-Portilla, Universidad Nacional de Colombia

Purpose

Financial technology (FinTech) has rapidly transformed the financial sector through innovations aimed at improving efficiency and accessibility (Su & Xu, 2023). Although often portrayed as an anti-corruption tool, FinTech can simultaneously open new avenues for misconduct (Brogi & Lagasio, 2024). Digital finance expansion has been associated with increased risks of financial fraud. For example, Buchak et al. (2018) observed a 30% rise in illegal fundraising activity in the U.S. between 2008 and 2015.

Measuring corruption and fraud remains a complex challenge due to their covert nature and contextual variability. Existing indices, such as the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) or the Control of Corruption Index (CCI), depend on perception surveys and lack granularity in sectoral analysis (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2015). This study introduces an alternative approach: a new indicator based on self-reported experiences shared on the social media platform X (formerly Twitter), focusing on financial corruption within the FinTech sector.

Research Design and Methods

We constructed a corruption and fraud indicator by analyzing Spanish-language posts from individual users between January 2015 and May 2024. Countries selected for analysis included the United States and the five most relevant Spanish-speaking FinTech markets: Spain, Mexico, Colombia, Argentina, and Chile. Posts were gathered via the X public API using Tweepy and filtered using keywords identified from expert interviews with financial regulators and FinTech executives.

To remove noise, we employed a bidirectional NLP filter. We selected the DeBERTa model (He et al., 2021) due to its superior performance in semantic understanding and positional encoding, improving upon

models such as BTTM (Li et al., 2020). For identifying patterns in types of fraud, we applied DBSCAN clustering using cosine distance, which is robust for arbitrary-shaped clusters and resilient to noise (Ester et al., 1996). The indicator was defined as a count of self-reported and machine-confirmed cases.

Finding and Results

From total relevant posts, just a 60% were identified as credible self-reports of corruption or fraud. The clustering algorithm distinguished three main fraud types: (1) hacking (e.g., malware, cloning, cyberattacks), (2) social engineering (e.g., phishing, scams), and (3) banking and card fraud (e.g., spoofing, unauthorized charges). An "unknown" category also emerged, possibly reflecting new or ambiguous forms of fraud. Reports showed a geographic bias toward urban centers, with limited representation from rural or remote areas due to the lack of geolocation metadata.

Originality and Contribution

This study offers a novel methodology to detect and classify financial fraud in the FinTech sector through social media data and advanced NLP techniques. Unlike conventional metrics relying on perceptions or official statistics, this approach leverages real-time, unsolicited reports from users to construct a contextualized and dynamic indicator. The combined use of DeBERTa and DBSCAN addresses prior limitations in fraud detection and enables granular insights into prevalent fraud modalities.

Implications

The proposed indicator offers a real-time tool that researchers, not just financial sector regulators, can use to monitor the dynamics of financial fraud. Unlike traditional data, which focuses on officially supervised entities, this indicator captures user complaints directed at both regulated and unregulated actors—many of which are active but invisible in official statistics. By leveraging self-reported experiences, this approach provides a more comprehensive view of fraud patterns. It opens up new opportunities for academic research, comparative studies across countries, and the construction of more accurate risk maps for financial integrity.

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7.2. Anatomy of Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Lending Fraud: A Review with Managerial Implications

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Introduction

This paper presents a systematic literature review (SLR) of fraud detection in P2P lending, a fast-growing alternative finance sector vulnerable to risks such as identity theft, misrepresentation, and Ponzi schemes. The study explores how machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) can be employed to mitigate fraud and highlights the lack of a standardized fraud definition. The authors identify the necessity of dynamic, explainable, and real-time fraud detection systems tailored to the behavioral and structural complexities of P2P environments.

Methodology

Using the Scopus database and a carefully constructed search query, the authors reviewed 134 papers and retained 38 after applying systematic inclusion and exclusion criteria. The review followed an eight-step SLR methodology, including problem formulation, research mapping, data collection, quality assessment, synthesis, and reporting. Key terms included 'Fraud,' 'P2P Lending,' and 'Alternative Finance.'

AI and ML in P2P Fraud Detection

The review reveals that AI/ML models, such as Random Forests, SVMs, XGBoost, and neural networks, are central to fraud detection in P2P platforms. AI allows real-time anomaly detection and supports pattern recognition across large transaction datasets. Yet, issues of transparency, bias, and model generalizability remain critical. Emerging techniques such as Explainable AI (XAI), graph attention networks, and hybrid rule-ML models are discussed as promising avenues.

Themes in Literature

Key fraud types include identity theft, misrepresentation, platform-level fraud (e.g., Ponzi schemes), and payment defaults. Fraud detection approaches span rule-based systems, reputation metrics, big data analytics, and supervised ML models. The literature also shows a geographic concentration of studies in China, highlighting the influence of regional regulation and data availability. Evaluation methods include empirical validation, simulations, and cross-platform comparisons.

Managerial and Consumer Implications

Managers of P2P platforms must prioritize investment in robust ML systems for fraud detection, align operations with evolving regulations, and implement trust and reputation mechanisms. Blockchain is recommended to enhance transactional integrity. The automation of fraud detection can also improve operational efficiency and scalability, making these systems essential for platform sustainability.

Conclusion

Fraud detection in P2P lending is a dynamic, interdisciplinary field combining finance, AI, and regulatory insight. While technological progress is evident, issues of data quality, model transparency, and ethical AI usage must be addressed. A standardized fraud definition and cross-platform benchmarks are essential for advancing the field.

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8. Parallel Paper Session 4A (08:30 -09:30)

“Equity Crowdfunding II”

Chair: *Dr. Artur Trzebiński*

8.1. Twin Transition and Equity Crowdfunding: A Legitimacy Theory

Perspective

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Purpose

This study explores the role of equity crowdfunding (ECF) in financing ventures aligned with the twin transition (TT), defined as the implementation/adoption of innovative digital technologies aiming at tackling environmental and social challenges (Diodato et al., 2023). The core research question is whether TT-oriented projects achieve better ECF outcomes than purely digital ones. To this end, drawing on legitimacy theory (Suchman, 1995), we hypothesize that the integration of sustainability attributes into digital projects enhances campaign performance through a synergistic effect of moral and pragmatic legitimacy. The presence of this positive sum game is empirically investigated.

Research Design and Methods

The analysis takes on a quantitative approach and bases on a dataset of 93 successfully funded digitalization projects (following the digital technology categorisation of He et al. (2024)) from European ECF platforms (2017–2024). Campaigns were manually categorized as TT by means of the binary variable *Sustainability*, following definitions in sustainable entrepreneurship literature (Shepherd and Patzelt, 2011). The dependent variable *Overfunding* was categorized into three ordinal levels (low, medium, high). An ordered probit regression was employed, incorporating controls such as *Team_Size*, *Company_Type* (Startup or SME), *Company_Location* (big city or countryside), *Minimum_Target* and *Minimum_Investment*, based

upon previous ECF literature (Ahlers et al., 2015; Vismara, 2019; Barbi & Mattioli, 2019). The marginal effects of *Sustainability* were investigated to measure its influence on overfunding probabilities.

Findings and Results

Contrary to the hypothesis, results indicate that displaying sustainable objectives reduces the likelihood of achieving high overfunding. While TT projects are more likely to meet or slightly exceed their funding targets, they are less likely to strongly outperform them. Marginal effects show a 19.5% increase in the probability of low overfunding and a -20.4% decrease for high overfunding when sustainability is present. These findings suggest that moral legitimacy enhances baseline success but may limit exceptional performance, possibly due to investor preference for technological over ethical appeals in high-return contexts (Le Pendeven & Schwienbacher, 2023).

Originality and Contribution

This is one of the first quantitative studies to evaluate TT's impact within ECF. Our results challenge existing literature (Yáñez-Valdés & Guerrero, 2024) claiming that sustainability and digitalization synergistically contribute to better fundraising results, offering new insights into the boundaries of moral and pragmatic legitimacy. It also introduces a novel methodological approach using the ordered probit to model non-linear success dynamics. This study contributes to both TT and crowdfunding literature by highlighting how sustainability may act more as a base legitimacy signal than as a driver of peak investor commitment.

Implications

For entrepreneurs, results indicate that adding sustainability to digital campaigns helps reach funding goals but may hinder peak overfunding. Strategic framing should balance social and environmental values with clear signals of scalability and profitability. For platforms, creating a TT category could support investor-campaign matching, improving visibility and trust. For policymakers, findings imply that sustainability

alone may not suffice to attract funding for startups and SMEs; targeted incentives or co-financing mechanisms may be required to close the legitimacy-performance gap of TT ventures.

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8.2. Strategic Intentional Signals: The Impact of the Disclosure of Intended

Use of Proceeds on Equity Crowdfunding Investors' Behaviour

Daniel Berliner, Tel-Hai Academic College, Israel

Purpose

The Use of Proceeds (UoP) section in an IPO prospectus plays a key role in informing investors how raised capital will be used. Transparent, growth-oriented allocations such as R&D, market expansion, or capital investment are generally favored, as they signal long-term potential and align with signalling theory. Conversely, allocations toward debt repayment often reduce investor confidence (Wyatt, 2014).

Equity crowdfunding (ECF) similarly depends on information disclosure, especially as retail investors seek clarity when evaluating early-stage ventures. This study explores how UoP disclosures in ECF influence investor behavior, drawing comparisons with IPOs to assess whether clearly defined fund allocations improve investor participation and campaign performance. The central research question asks whether UoP disclosures predict investor behavior in ECF contexts (Hornuf & Schwienbacher, 2018).

Research Design and Methods

This study uses a unique dataset from the Pipelbiz platform, comprising 9,021 investment decisions made by 5,649 investors across 39 technology-based ECF campaigns conducted between July 2018 and December 2020. We analyze three dependent variables reflecting investor behavior: (1) investment amount (USD pledged), (2) investment ratio (relative to platform minimum), and (3) timing of investment (days until campaign ends). The main explanatory variables capture intended UoP, categorized into three groups: investment (e.g., R&D, production), marketing (e.g., sales, business development), and general purposes (e.g., OPEX).

Findings and Results

Using multiple linear regressions, the study examined how the intended UoP in ECF campaigns affects investor behavior, measured by investment amount, investment ratio (relative to minimum), and timing.

The results show that growth-oriented UoP, such as R&D, patents, clinical trials, business development, and production, generally increase investment amounts. However, their effects on timing and proportional investment vary. For example, patents encourage early, above-minimum investments, while R&D and clinical trials are linked to later investments and lower ratios, possibly reflecting investor caution or uncertainty. In addition, marketing and sales-related spending increases investment amounts and encourages early participation, but does not lead to higher-than-minimum contributions. Conversely, we found a negative effect of general and administrative (G&A) and operating expenses (OPEX) on investment size. Although these uses occasionally lead to modest increases in the investment ratio or early investment, they are generally viewed as less value-creating. In addition, demographic factors show that older investors invest more, while female investors tend to invest less and at lower ratios.

Originality and Contribution

This study highlights the importance of the declared intended UoP in shaping ECF investor behavior. Investors favor growth-oriented and marketing-related spending, which leads to higher individual investment amounts, while allocations to working capital tend to deter investment. These findings offer practical insights for entrepreneurs aiming to align their UoP disclosures with investor preferences to improve campaign success.

Implications

Early-stage ventures can improve their funding success by aligning campaigns with investors' preference for growth-oriented UoP. ECF platforms can support this by structuring campaign pages to address investor concerns and reduce rejection rates.

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9. Parallel Paper Session 4B (08:30 -09:30)

“Digital and Crowdlending”

Chair: *Dr. Urszula Mrzygłód*

9.1. Consumer spending behavior in ‘Buy Now Pay Later’ model: A comparative analysis between China and Norway

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Rotem Shneor, University of Agder, Norway

Purpose

This study investigates how cognitive and affective factors contribute to the spending patterns of BNPL users. An extended framework of Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) is applied to analyze user behavior in BNPL services. In addition, a comparative analysis seeks to examine whether these effects exhibit uniformity across countries or whether variations emerge due to different national contexts.

Research Design and Methods

Data was collected from a web-based survey distributed in China and Norway, including respondents’ demographic features, spending habits and affective feedback. After processing, the final sample consists of 488 cases in China and 497 cases in Norway. A series of essential tests were also conducted: Normality test, EFA, CFA, Reliability test, Validity test, Response Bias and Common Method Bias tests. Then Structural Equation Modeling was employed to analyze the drivers of two dependent variables: average spending amount and total spending amount. Finally, regression results were compared across two countries.

Findings and Results

Overall, the results show that perceived usefulness contributes positively to both average and total BNPL spending, and invariant relation is discovered across contexts. Perceived ease of use is negatively related to average BNPL spending in China, while the relations become positive and stronger for total spending in China than Norway. Satisfaction with traditional finance is found to have a negative influence on total spending in Norway. In contrast, satisfaction with BNPL services is positively associated with average BNPL expenditures in China and with total spending in Norway. For indirect relations, the effect of

perceived ease of use is significantly positive in China but negative in Norway. Also, no significant difference between the two economies is found regarding the influence of low credit score on average spending. Impulse level is found to only boost average and total spending in Norway. Finally, interaction effects function differently in two contexts.

Originality and Contribution

This study is among the first to examine the cross-cultural validity of the extended TAM model developed for the BNPL context. It offers valuable insights into how digital finance functions in contrasting economic and cultural environments, providing a basis for generalization to other economies. In addition, by incorporating satisfaction, this study supplements cognitive with affective antecedents of technology engagement. Specifically, we explored positive or negative affective states proposed by (Hoong et al., 2017) in their affective TAM, bridging the gap between post-adoption behavior and TAM and enhancing its ability to explain long-term user engagement. Moreover, this also introduces a new dimension that accounts for users' intuitive and spontaneous decisions, which allows TAM to capture the role of non-rational factors and offers a more comprehensive understanding of user behavior.

Implications

For researchers, this study encourages deeper exploration of BNPL consumer behavior from cultural, institutional and psychological perspectives. It also offers practical insights for service providers to tailor their marketing strategies while considering distinct cultural preferences.

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9.2. Digital Bonds: The Role of Costs and Document Information on Trading

Volume

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Purpose

This study investigates how cost structures and product documentation quality influence trading activity in tokenized treasury products issued on public blockchains. It seeks to understand the microstructure of decentralized fixed-income markets by identifying which frictions, including transaction costs, management fees, and disclosure content, facilitate or hinder market participation.

Research Design and Methods

Using a unique dataset of 7,719 transactions from 22 tokenized U.S. Treasury products on Ethereum and Polygon, the paper employs multivariate OLS and IV regressions. To measure disclosure informativeness, the study leverages large language models (LLMs) to simulate investor interpretation of legal, financial, and technological documentation. Placebo simulations and heterogeneity analyses are conducted to validate the robustness and generalizability of the results.

Findings and Results

Higher transaction costs reduce trading volume, while management fees are positively associated with volume, especially when financial documentation is informative. Legal disclosures, by contrast, appear to dampen participation. Heterogeneity analysis reveals that fee sensitivity varies by region, investor access, asset structure, and stablecoin support. Instrumental variable estimates and placebo tests confirm the robustness of these core relationships.

Originality and Contribution

This paper is among the first to systematically study real-world trading behavior in blockchain-based treasury markets. It introduces a novel AI-based approach to quantify the informativeness of product documentation and disentangles how disclosure types interact with cost perceptions. By bridging understanding from digital finance, financial disclosure, and DeFi microstructure, the paper advances empirical understanding of tokenized assets.

Implications

The findings emphasize the importance of reducing transaction frictions and improving documentation clarity to enhance market participation. Regulators and product designers must recognize that investor response to fees and disclosures is highly context dependent. The study also illustrates the practical value of AI-driven text analysis for financial supervision, communication design, and infrastructure policy in emerging digital markets.

10. Parallel Paper Session 5A (09:50 -11:10)

“Blockchain Finance”

Chair: *Dr. Ramy Elitzur*

10.1. Vote Delegation in DeFi Governance

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Abstract

We investigate the drivers of vote delegation in Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAOs), using the Uniswap governance DAO as a laboratory. We show that parties with fewer self-owned votes and those affiliated with the controlling venture capital firm, Andreessen Horowitz (a16z), receive more vote delegations. These patterns suggest that while the Uniswap ecosystem values decentralization, a16z may engage in window-dressing around it. Moreover, we find that an active and successful track record in submitting improvement proposals, especially in the final stage, leads to more vote delegations, indicating that delegation in DAOs is at least partly reputation- or merit-based. Combined, our findings provide new insights into how governance and decentralization operate in DeFi.

10.2. Real Estate Tokens: Evaluating Long-Term Relationships with Major

Asset Classes

Fatemeh Mottaghi, KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Bertram Steininger, KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Purpose

Emerging new technologies like blockchain, smart contracts and tokenization offer a new form of real estate investment that is faster, cheaper, and more transparent (Mottaghi et al., 2024; Baum, 2021). This paper investigates the long-term relationships between real estate tokens and traditional financial market indicators such as REITs, GDP, oil, gold, S&P 500, and S&P Crypto 10, building on prior work exploring the characteristics of real estate token markets (i.e., Abdullah et al., 2023; Kreppmeier et al., 2023; Steininger, 2023).

Research Design and Methods

A dataset of monthly data from November 2019 to January 2024 was constructed, including a value-weighted real estate token index developed by the authors from 50,288 daily records. Stationarity tests (ADF, KPSS, PP) confirmed all variables as I(1). The study employed Johansen's cointegration test and VECM to explore the existence and nature of long-term equilibrium relationships. Additionally, a novel nonlinear extension, the COINtensity VECM, was applied to capture the time-varying strength of these relationships across different economic periods.

Findings and Results

The analysis revealed three statistically significant cointegration relationships among the studied assets. Both traditional (REITs, GDP) and emerging (real estate tokens) assets were found to be influenced by long-term stochastic trends. Notably, real estate tokens showed weaker but statistically significant integration compared to REITs. Dynamic analysis showed fluctuations in the cointegration intensity, with peaks during the COVID-19 crisis and declines in post-crisis periods. Structural break analysis identified

two major shifts in cointegration intensity: May 2020 and January 2022. Granger causality tests revealed that the cointegration intensity predicted changes in key volatility indices (e.g., VIX, DJIA VIX, Oil VIX), but not vice versa.

Originality and Contribution

This study is among the first to empirically assess the evolving long-term interactions between real estate tokens and major asset classes. The use of COINtensity VECM provides a dynamic perspective that goes beyond traditional static models. The findings contribute to a better understanding of how tokenized real estate is gradually integrating into the broader financial ecosystem and how it responds to systemic market shocks.

Implications

The results have important implications for investors, policymakers, and regulators. Investors can use the insights to manage portfolio diversification and systemic risk, especially during volatile market periods. Policymakers and regulators are provided with evidence of the increasing structural integration of tokenized real estate into global markets, which may inform future regulatory frameworks and risk monitoring.

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10.3. Bridging Traditional and Digital Assets: An Entropy Analysis of Real

Estate Tokens and Financial Market Dynamics

Fatemeh Mottaghi, KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Bertram Steininger, KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Purpose

This study investigates the dynamics of information transmission between tokenized real estate assets (real estate tokens) and both traditional and digital financial markets. The main objective is to understand how real estate tokens interact with established markets like REITs, stock indices (S&P 500, Russell 2000), commodities (gold, oil), and Ethereum-based digital assets (S&P Ethereum), particularly during periods of financial turbulence, building on recent work exploring tokenized real estate markets (i.e., Baum, 2021; Kreppmeier et al., 2023; Mottaghi et al., 2024).

Research Design and Methods

The study applies entropy-based techniques—transfer entropy, conditional entropy, and mutual information—to quantify the directionality and intensity of information flow between asset classes. A dataset of monthly data from November 2019 to January 2024, including 50,288 daily records of real estate tokens, was used to construct a value-weighted real estate token index. Stationarity tests were conducted, and since the series were found to be integrated of order one, the analysis was performed on first-differenced data to ensure validity of the entropy measures. Dynamic information flow analysis was further performed using sliding window conditional entropy to assess how relationships evolved pre-, during, and post-COVID-19.

Findings and Results

Results show that real estate tokens primarily act as information receivers. Significant information flows were observed from small-cap equities (Russell 2000) and Ethereum-based digital assets (SP ETH) to real estate tokens, especially after the COVID-19 crisis, highlighting a shift towards increasing influence of

digital markets. No strong bidirectional flow was detected between real estate tokens and REITs, indicating distinct market behaviors. Conditional entropy analysis confirmed these relationships and revealed that inflationary pressures (CPI) indirectly affect tokenized real estate via their impact on equity and crypto markets. Robustness checks using Rényi entropy validated the stability of these findings.

Originality and Contribution

This paper is one of the first to comprehensively apply entropy-based methods to examine the informational interconnectedness of real estate tokens within global financial markets. It offers novel empirical evidence that tokenized real estate represents a unique, emerging asset class with dependencies distinct from traditional real estate investments like REITs. The study contributes significantly to the growing body of knowledge on DeFi and tokenized assets, providing actionable insights into risk diversification, portfolio optimization, and systemic risk assessment in digital finance.

Implications

The findings have important implications for investors, policymakers, and regulators. Real estate tokens' dependence on digital asset markets suggests that traditional real estate portfolio models may not yet treat them as substitutes for REITs. Portfolio managers should consider the speculative and liquidity-driven nature of tokenized assets. Policymakers and regulators are advised to monitor systemic risks arising from the integration of tokenized assets into global financial systems. Future research is recommended to explore longer time horizons, real-time investor sentiment, and regulatory impacts on tokenized real estate market stability.

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10.4. The Optimal Long-term Portfolio Share of Bitcoin is Negative (or Zero)

Alistair Milne, Loughborough University

Objective and research design

This paper analyses the optimal share of Bitcoin BTC for a long-term investor combining Bitcoin with exposure to the US S&P 500 equity index, in the standard Markovitz mean-variance portfolio framework. Past returns are not necessarily a good guide to future returns, especially for a new asset such as Bitcoin; extrapolating past growth forward Bitcoin would be worth global GDP in only This analysis instead assumes that the expected price of investment assets grow, over the decades ahead, in line with US nominal GDP (assumed to be 5% per annum, though the results are not sensitive to this growth rate). This is an implication of fundamental based asset pricing theory, assuming no change in investor risk-return preferences or other structural determinants of asset prices, There is still a difference in returns: equities generate dividend payments, in line with recent past 1.5% of market valuation per annum, so offer total returns of 6.5% per annum; Bitcoin offers no income, relying solely on capital gains, so offering total returns of 5% per annum. Risk estimates are, in contrast, data based, using two estimation windows Feb 2014-Feb 2025 and Feb 2020- Feb 2025:

Metric	2014-2025		2020-2025	
	S&P500	BTC	S&P500	BTC
Variance-	1.15×10^{-4}	0.94×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-4}	2.04×10^{-4}
Covariance		18.74×10^{-4}		16.48×10^{-4}
Standard deviation	1.072%	4.329%	1.319%	4.059%
Skew	-0.54	0.02	-0.52	-0.56
Kurtosis	15.7	6.8	13.7	9.5
Sharpe ratio	2.70%	0.51%	2.19%	0.51%
Correlation	0.202		0.381	

Table 1: Statistical metrics of daily returns on S&P500 composite and Bitcoin

Findings and implications

With these assumptions the optimal portfolio share of Bitcoin for investors with a long-term investment horizon is negative, -1.6% (with the longer estimation window) and -7.3% (with the shorter window). Other studies report that a positive BTC portfolio share improves risk-return trade-offs (e.g. Kajtazi and Moro 2019; Huang et al. 2023)). This is because those other studies focus on short-term dynamic asset allocation strategies and do not employ the more recent data used here, exhibiting an increased +ve correlation between BTC and stock returns. The findings here are similar to but extend those of Baur et al. 2022.

Two propositions based on the two-asset Markovitz portfolio provide intuitive insight. Proposition 1 shows that the variance minimizing portfolio share of BTC is negative when the covariance between BTC and the S&P500 exceeds the variance of the S&P500. Proposition 2 shows that optimal share of the BTC is negative so long as the ratio of covariance to variance exceeds the ratio of the BTC to the S&P500 risk-premium. If the risk free rate exceeds the long-term growth of asset prices then the risk-premium on BTC is negative and any positive correlation with the S&P500 requires a negative BTC portfolio share.

In practice, because of model uncertainty a zero rather than negative BTC share is appropriate for long-term investors. BTC should, at least for now, be viewed as a purely speculative asset.

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11. Parallel Paper Session 5B (09:50 -11:10)

“Microfinance”

Chair: *Dr. Samuel Nyarko*

11.1. Technology Adoption in the Indian Microfinance Industry: Issues and Way Forward for the Indian NBFC-MFIs, a Cross-Case Analysis.

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Dr. Anil Mishra, Management Development Institute, Gurgaon. India

Amanpreet Kaur, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India

Purpose

Technology has been a major catalyst in bringing MFI loans to rural and low-income groups in the Indian microfinance sector. Microfinance institutions (MFIs) now use digital tools to transform how they provide loans and interface with customers. The process has not been smooth sailing and had its ups and downs in this financial inclusion journey in the microfinance sector. MFIs still face major hurdles in fully integrating technology into their fabric. By providing an account of where Indian microfinance stands on its digital journey this qualitative research unravels the major issues and challenges faced by a representative sample of 5 Indian NBFC-MFIs, 4 major Fintech service providers, and 6 industry experts. Using a comprehensive multiple-case design of qualitative research and interviews, this inductive study examines the phenomenon from multiple vantage points and levels of analysis. The study opens up new and unexplored possibilities in the Indian context, where a research gap was identified by the lack of existing literature and structured data, which made this study necessary. The sector's lack of digital and financial literacy is one of the main issues, which is why customers of the institutions are reluctant to accept new technologies. In many ways, the research contributes to the development of the viewpoint for elevating the practice. It would pave the path for other MFIs that are still using traditional delivery channels and persuade them to join the league by demonstrating the value of technology-driven procedures.

By accelerating and securing financial operations, it would direct them to adopt new technology-driven business models that would improve customer experience and support service transformation. Our findings point to a few strategies that can be used to address the industry's current problems. Hence achieving the

integral milestone of social and economic development through digital financial inclusion and promoting efficiency, inclusion and innovation in the economy.

Research Design and Methods

We made an inductive study using a holistic multiple case design of qualitative research, to study the phenomenon from multi-dimensional perspectives and levels of analysis (Yin, 1994; Miles Huberman, 1984, 1994), and collective and instrumental case study method (Stake, 2000). The research started with the preparation of an exhaustive case study protocol (Eisenhardt, 1989; Yin, 1994; Miles and Huberman, 1994; Maimbo and Pervan, 2005)

Findings and Results

Our results highlight some of the initiatives that can be adopted to combat the prevailing challenges of the sector. Lack of digital and financial literacy within the sector is one of the key challenges due to which resistance to technology adoption can be witnessed among the customers of the institutions. To conquer these challenges, applications should be designed with a user-friendly interface that aims to bring last-mile connectivity. Services should be offered in vernacular languages to promote adoption, and voice-based transactions and interactive sessions should be incorporated. The introduction of hyper-personalised and innovative products can be used as an incentive to attract customer attention and ensure customer engagement. Young members of the family should be encouraged to use digital modes of financial transactions. Small and Medium MFIs can reduce their operational and technology implementation costs by using single co-shared platforms among them. A unified and standard model of credit assessments should also be implemented within the sector to assess household income and repayment capacity of the customers, as it is difficult to rely upon the self-reported data of the customers. Also, to reduce the instances of multiple lending, the new documents given by the customer should be verified with their previously submitted record, to check against duplicate identities. Regulatory guidelines and their compliances are becoming complex with time. These regulations are sometimes interpreted differently by different

institutions, which bring ambiguity in the sector. As an initiative, representatives from the Self-Regulatory Organisations (SROs) and microfinance institutions must be involved in decision-making or policy implementation by the regulators to consider their perspectives as well.

Originality and Contribution

This is an original piece of works covering the issues and challenges related to the technology adoption in the NBFC-MFI sector of India. It is novel in its approach and brings in realistic picture as well prescriptive policy framework for the sector.

Implications

The research has far reaching implications for the industry it talks about facilitative regulatory policies by the Reserve Bank of India while maintaining stringency in client protection and the evolving role of the SROs which ensure the implementation of regulations the Indian microfinance industry has come a long way.

The Industry certainly is steadfast in sustainably implementing the financial inclusion objective, propelled by a number of shifts toward ecosystems, collaborations, alliances, and digital enablement, in addition to developments in regulatory aspects. Through innovation, teamwork, digital transformation, and skill development, technology-based interventions could further enhance last-mile connectivity for under banked customers and help in providing higher levels of efficiency, innovation, and Financial inclusion 2.0. NBFC-MFIs must, however, evaluate the escalating competition from other Small Finance Banks and FinTechs as well as from other established MFIs and other players in the market and deal with industry-specific issues. In order to improve product uptake, NBFC-MFIs should concentrate on developing more safe, tailored solutions for their clients in tandem with the Fintech arms that satisfy the requirements of scalability and dependability and drive the cause of Financial Inclusion 2.0. Thereby proving to be a crucial industry which would boost in making the Indian economy achieve its \$ 5 trillion mark.

Keywords: Technology Adoption, Non-Banking Financial Company-Microfinance Institutions (NBFC-MFIs), Fintech Service Providers.

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12. Parallel Paper Session 5C (09:50 -11:10)

“Insights from Crowdfunding Practice”

Chair: *Dr. Eliran Solodoha*

12.1. Can Generative AI Read the Crowd? Reimagining Crowdfunding

Signals and Backer Insight

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Purpose

This study investigates the predictive capabilities of generative artificial intelligence (AI)—specifically ChatGPT—in forecasting the success of crowdfunding campaigns on Kickstarter. Anchored in Signaling Theory (Spence, 1973), it examines whether AI-generated signals align with established indicators of campaign support and how such tools might enhance or interfere with the heuristic-based decision-making processes of potential backers (Cumming et al., 2025).

Research Design and Methods

We analyzed a sample of 300 Kickstarter campaigns launched in December 2024. For each campaign, ChatGPT generated ex-ante predictions for key outcome variables, including the probability of success, number of comments, and expected funds raised (cf. Elitzur & Solodoha, 2021; Liran & Eliran, 2025; Shneor & Vik, 2020). We explored two core questions:

1. How does ChatGPT predict the success of Kickstarter campaigns, and what factors drive its assessments?
2. Do ChatGPT's predictions replace or complement established crowdfunding signals in traditional predictive models?

To address the second question, we integrated GPT-generated features into deep learning models (JMP® Pro 18.1.2 with the Torch Add-In) and evaluated their performance. Model accuracy was assessed based on how well they classified successful campaigns and forecasted funding outcomes, highlighting the complementary role of AI-generated signals in data-driven decision frameworks.

Findings and Results

Consistent with prior research, traditional variables—such as project category, geographic location, and funding goal—remained the most reliable predictors of crowdfunding success. However, the integration of GPT-derived features added **incremental explanatory power**, altering the relative influence of several secondary predictors. Notably, GPT’s forecasts for engagement-related metrics—such as the expected number of updates and comments—closely mirrored actual outcomes, highlighting the significance of communication signals in backer decision-making.

While GPT’s overall predictions showed strong alignment with real results, they tended to be **overly optimistic**, positioning the model more as an enthusiastic supporter than a cautious evaluator. Nonetheless, incorporating GPT outputs modestly improved model accuracy and shifted predictive emphasis toward **behavioral and interaction-based cues**, rather than surface-level features. Robustness checks confirmed the stability of these patterns across multiple outcome measures.

Originality and Contribution

This research extends Signaling Theory into the domain of generative AI, demonstrating how models like GPT interpret and prioritize crowdfunding signals. While GPT does not outperform traditional predictors in terms of accuracy, its inclusion **reshapes the relative importance of signals** and draws attention to previously underemphasized features (Yang et al., 2025). By integrating GPT-derived insights into **deep learning models**, the study contributes a novel methodological approach that blends human-like language understanding with advanced pattern recognition. This dual-layered analysis offers fresh insight into campaign dynamics and backer behavior, enriching both the crowdfunding and entrepreneurial finance literatures.

Implications

The findings suggest that GPT serves as a **complement** rather than a substitute for human or data-driven judgment. For **campaign creators**, AI tools emphasize the importance of clear communication, compelling narratives, and strong visual presentation. For **potential backers**, GPT-generated insights provide scalable

heuristics that can guide decisions in environments characterized by information asymmetry. For **crowdfunding platforms**, generative AI offers new opportunities for content curation, early-stage campaign screening, and quality assurance. However, these advantages must be carefully balanced against ongoing concerns around **algorithmic bias**, **interpretability**, and **transparency** (Chila et al., 2025).

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12.2. Crowdfunding Beyond Borders: Geographic Disparities in

Crowdfunding Success

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Eliran Solodoha, Peres Academic Center, Rehovot, Israel

Purpose

This study investigates how geographic location affects crowdfunding success by analyzing the differential interpretation of entrepreneurial signals in central versus peripheral regions. Drawing on Regional Development Theory (Carbonara, 2021) and Signaling Theory (Spence, 1978), the research explores how structural disparities impact entrepreneurs' ability to attract backers on digital platforms, particularly in the context of reward-based crowdfunding.

Research Design and Methods

The study utilizes a dataset of 2,578 campaigns launched between 2012 and 2022 on Headstart, Israel's leading rewards-based crowdfunding platform. We matched campaign data with the Israeli Central Bureau of Statistics Peripherality Index, which ranks localities by accessibility and proximity to Tel Aviv, the country's economic hub. Two dependent variables were examined: (1) percentage of funding target achieved, and (2) number of investors per funding goal. We employed OLS regressions with interaction terms to test whether the effectiveness of signals—such as prior entrepreneurial experience, number of reward tiers, and use of video—varied based on geographic context (e.g., Elitzur, R., & Solodoha, 2021; Solodoha; 2024; Solodoha, E., & Blaywais, 2023; Tang et al., 2022).

Findings and Results

The analysis shows that campaigns from central regions consistently outperform those from peripheral areas in terms of both funding success and backer engagement. While the proportion of campaigns from peripheral areas increased significantly over the years (17.2% in 2012 to 61.2% in 2022), these ventures faced systemic challenges such as reduced visibility and weaker social networks. Moreover, the

effectiveness of signals differed sharply by geography. In central regions, prior experience and reward diversity were positively and significantly associated with outcomes, while in peripheral regions, these same signals had no or weaker effects, suggesting that structural disadvantages limit their interpretive power. Notably, video usage had no significant impact in either context, echoing recent work questioning the universal value of audiovisual signals.

Originality and Contribution

This study extends crowdfunding research by shifting the analytical lens from backer-centric models to the entrepreneur's geographic context, revealing how spatial dynamics shape signaling outcomes. The integration of Regional Development and Signaling Theory offers a richer understanding of how digital inequality persists even in supposedly "borderless" crowdfunding ecosystems (e.g., Georgallis & Durand, 2017; Solodoha, 2022). Empirically, it provides the first large-scale study of geographic signal effectiveness in Israel's crowdfunding landscape.

Implications

For platforms, the results highlight the need for algorithmic adjustments and visibility tools to support peripheral campaigns. For policymakers, investing in digital infrastructure and developing localized training programs may help peripheral entrepreneurs leverage their signals more effectively. For researchers, the study opens new avenues for examining how location-based disparities interact with digital entrepreneurial behaviors.

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12.3. Value Co-creation in Crowdfunding: A Systematic Literature Review

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Purpose

A large chunk of the literature on crowdfunding studies its financial success or the factors influencing the contribution of individual backers; in both cases, the implication appears to be that financial contribution is the most important element of crowdfunding. In this paper we attempt to go beyond crowdfunding success and contribution: applying the framework of value co-creation, we (1) create a taxonomy of more-than-financial elements of crowdfunding, (2) identify their antecedents and (3) classify their consequences.

Research Design and Methods

We conducted a Systematic Literature Review and identified papers in the crowdfunding area that included co-creation, either openly or by mentioning some adjacent topic such as “engagement” or “information sharing”. Out of 363 papers returned by the search query, we proceeded to include in this study 47 high-quality papers where co-creation figured as a variable. We coded the relevant information in each paper and proceeded with a systematic analysis.

Findings and Results

Our findings cover a wide array of topics. First, we discovered a fragmented corpus of literature, where the idea of co-creation is not used homogeneously and similar variables hide small differences in their composition. Second, there is a clear positive bias, where almost all relationships studied were between positive antecedents and positive outcomes. Third, a total of 60 variables referring to co-creation were studied, with 55 antecedents and 56 consequences; while the antecedents were varied, covering many elements of psychology and behavior, consequences were strongly focused on crowdfunding success, showing that even within co-creation the goal is always the maximization of contributions.

Originality and Contributions

This is the first time to the best of our knowledge that a paper attempts to collect all the literature around co-creation in crowdfunding. We believe that this offers three main contributions. First, it allows to observe a uniform picture of the current state-of-the-art. Second, we offer in each sub-section of the paper a list of suggested research gaps that could warrant further exploration by other scholars interested in the topic. Third, the findings from this paper can be expanded outside of crowdfunding: other ecosystems can present similar dynamics to those that are hereby discussed.

Implications

Besides showing the relevance of the co-creation framework when analyzing more-than-financial elements in the crowdfunding ecosystem, this paper attempts to also offer practical implications for platform and creators, in order to maximize the non-monetary value that they are able to co-create with the ecosystem.

13. Parallel Paper Session 6A (15.00 -15:40)

“Crowdfunding Adoption”

Chair: *Dr. Joanna Adamska*

13.1. Determinants and Consequences of Crowdfunding Awareness among Prospective Backers

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Abstract

Crowdfunding offers opportunities for overcoming limitations in access to entrepreneurial finance. Its success depends on wide-scale adoption by prospective backers to unleash the “power of the crowd”. Such adoption is particularly challenging in societies characterized by low levels of social trust. The current study suggests and tests a model inspired by innovation adoption theory for capturing key determinants and consequences of crowdfunding awareness, which, in turn, shape prospective backers’ attitudes and contribution intentions. This model is tested using SEM procedures on a sample of 960 prospective backers from five low trust societies: Ghana, Tanzania, Morocco, DR Congo and Israel. We present several consistent findings in all five contexts of study. First, in terms of determinants, crowdfunding awareness is positively and significantly associated with economic education, familiarity with fundraisers, and perceived levels of social trust. Second, in terms of consequences, interest and attitudes are significantly and positively associated with crowdfunding awareness. And third, the effects of crowdfunding awareness on intentions are fully mediated by both attitudes and interest.

14. Parallel Paper Session 6B (15.00 -15:40)

“Beyond the Campaign”
Chair: *Dr. Maria Jose Quero*

14.1. Maximize reach over contribution size: Exploring campaign

characteristics in the success of market entry post-crowdfunding

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Karsten Wenzlaff, University of Hamburg

Purpose

There is an apparent flaw in the reward-based crowdfunding literature: studies on crowdfunding overfocus on the campaign stage (Arshad, Shneor, & Berndt, 2023), which involves engaging potential backers and securing financial contributions. The crowdfunding process includes three stages: (1) ideation to campaign launch, (2) the crowdfunding campaign and (3) post-campaign to product delivery. Thus, collecting funds, stage 2, is only a minor part of the crowdfunding process. Our contribution lies in extending the analysis of crowdfunding success (i.e. stage 2) to the post-campaign stage (i.e. stage 3). In the context of product development, we seek to provide an overview of which outcomes of the campaign stage connect with market entry in the post-campaign stage, thus adding to our understanding of the overall success of the crowdfunding process. We focus on the following research question: *“Which characteristics of the campaign stage connect with the post-campaign market entry stage?”*

Research design and methods

We analyze the market entry phase of products from 335 successfully financed projects on Kickstarter. Using an online search, we collected observational data and connected market entry to campaign characteristics. Our data includes campaign characteristics visible on the campaign website (i.e. number of donors, average donation amount, number of comments). Market entry was operationalized by ‘offering the product central to the crowdfunding campaign for sale online’. If this was the case, it was assigned a ‘1’ (yes market entry); if not, it was assigned a ‘0’ (no market entry). We followed a four-step process of searching the web to determine this manually.

Results

Our most basic observation of the data shows that 43% of the included campaigns reached the market entry stage. Thus, less than half of the campaigns did not succeed in offering the product, that was presented during the crowdfunding campaign, for sale on an online platform. Running a Mann-Whitney U test, we found that the total collected contributions is significantly higher among projects that entered the market (Mdn = 102,261.00, SD = 372,985.17) compared to those projects that did not enter the market (Mdn = 57,806.00, SD = 296,035.03), $U = 10,536.50$, $n = 335$, $p < .001$. The difference is likely because of a higher number of contributors rather than a higher average contribution amount. Running a Mann-Whitney U test, we found that the number of contributors is significantly higher among projects that entered the market (Mdn = 825.00, SD = 2,309.90) than those projects that did not enter the market (Mdn = 439.50, SD = 2,103.20), $U = 10,205.00$, $n = 335$, $p < .001$. On the other hand, running a Mann-Whitney U test, we found that there is no significant difference for the contribution amount ($U = 13,411.50$, $n = 335$, $p = .718$), with projects entering the market (Mdn = 132.57, SD = 162.48) collecting similar amounts as those that did not enter the market (Mdn = 130.99, SD = 192.04).

Contribution and implications

Our findings suggest that successfully completing the campaign stage does not guarantee a project's entry into the market, as approximately 57% of the projects did not make it to the market. In addition, our findings show that the number of donors is the only campaign characteristic connected with market entry: projects with successful market entry had a higher number of donors than those that did not enter the market. The average contribution amount had no connection with market entry. Together, these findings suggest that a broad support base is more important than a high-value one.

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14.2. Post-fundraising performance of equity crowdfunded firms: The role of professional investors

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Cheema, M. A., University of Otago, New Zealand

Tom Vanacker, Ghent University, Belgium

Purpose

This paper investigates the heterogeneity in post-campaign outcomes across equity crowdfunded (ECF) firms, in particular the role of venture capitalists (VCs) and business angels (BAs) in ECF firms. We also consider the role of syndication (i.e., multiple VCs or multiple BAs investing together) and co-investment (i.e., VC(s) and BA(s) investing together) practices in the ECF market.

Research Design and Methods

Drawing on a dataset of 1,185 UK ECF firms that successfully raised funds between 2011 and 2022, the study tracks their post-campaign outcomes in terms of size, financial profitability, innovation, and entrepreneurial finance events (i.e., follow-on fundraising, M&As, or IPOs). We use the entropy balancing matching approach introduced by e.g., Hainmueller (2012) to enhance covariate balance and accuracy in matching, reducing the loss of observations. We match ECF firms backed by BAs and VCs with ECF firms without such investors using three criteria: sector classification, campaign size, and firm age. After matching, we employ a year and sector fixed-effect regression.

Findings and Results

Our analyses show that BA-backed and VC-backed ECF firms have larger post-campaign employment compared to matched ECF firms without such investors. We fail to find significant differences in financial performance between BA- or VC-backed ECF firms and matched firms without such backing. For innovation, we find that BA- and VC-backed firms, if anything, have lower intangible asset ratios and granted patents, respectively, compared to their matched counterparts. ECF firms with multiple investors

of the same type (i.e., VCs or BAs) have more total assets and higher employment but fewer patents compared to ECF firms without such investors. ECF firms backed by distinct investor types (i.e., both VC(s) and BA(s)) have fewer employees, lower financial performance, and fewer granted patents compared to ECF firms without such investors. Interestingly, while we find no significant effect for ECF firms with BA-backing only, those with VC-backing only, a syndicate of BAs or VCs, or VC-BA co-investment all outperform ECF firms without such investors in terms of the likelihood of future entrepreneurial finance events.

Originality and Contribution

Our study contributes to the equity crowdfunding and entrepreneurial finance literature in several important ways. First, we present novel evidence on the role of VCs and BAs in shaping the post-campaign outcomes of ECF firms (e.g., Signori & Vismara, 2018), offering granular insights into how these distinct investor types, individually and in combination (i.e., syndication or co-investment), affect ECF firm outcomes. Second, our paper responds to recent calls for more research into co-investment dynamics between heterogeneous investor types (e.g., Manigart & Khosravi, 2023; Wallmeroth et al., 2018), showing that co-invested ECF firms exhibit distinctive patterns of outcomes (e.g., in total assets, employment, and entrepreneurial finance events).

Implications

For entrepreneurs, our findings suggest that the presence of VCs or BAs in ECF campaigns is not a guarantee for post-campaign performance. Entrepreneurs should therefore proactively seek strategic engagement and post-investment support, not just capital. For retail investors, they should evaluate the broader investment proposition, including product-market fit, team experience, and post-campaign plans. Additionally, both entrepreneurs and investors must recognize the potential tensions that can arise in heterogeneous investor syndicates and structure governance accordingly.

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